

Assay of some new antibiotic drugs in pure form and in their pharmaceutical preparations by using Cu^{III} reagent

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Abstract : In the present paper we have reported a simple and convenient titrimetric method for the determination of some antibiotic drugs in pure form and in their pharmaceutical preparations i.e. Azithromycin, Azenam, Kanamycin sulphate, Gemifloxacin and Clindamycin with potassiumdipertelluratocuprate(III) as an oxidizing reagent. The present reagent is being used for the oxidation of several class of organic compounds. Aliquots containing 1–5 mg of the sample were taken in 100 mL stoppered conical flask, 5 ml of 0.035 N potassiumdipertelluratocuprate(III) and 10 mL of 5 N H_2SO_4 was added to it. The reaction mixture was shaken thoroughly and allowed to react for required reaction time (5–15 min) at room temperature (25–30 °C). After the reaction was over 5 mL of 10% KI solution was added to it. Contents shaken thoroughly and allowed to stand for a minute. The liberated iodine was titrated with 0.01 N sodium thiosulphate using starch as indicator. During estimation it was noted that the excipients present in pharmaceutical preparations do not interfere. The value of percentage error, standard deviation (SD) and coefficient of variation prove the method to be precise and reproducible. To establish authenticity of the method, recovery experiments were also carried out by standard drug addition method. In Indian Pharmacopoeia (IP) 2007, Vol. 2, the determination of Azithromycin tablets is given by liquid chromatography (page 761) and Kanamycin injections by thin layer chromatography (page 1263). For other antibiotics there is no method available in IP.

Keywords : Antibiotic drugs, potassiumdipertelluratocuprate(III) reagent, titration.

Introduction

Antibiotics are used for diminishing or preventing the body against microorganism i.e. virus and bacteria. Because of their medicinal importance their determination has widely been studied^{1–3}. In this paper we describe determination of following drugs – Azithromycin⁴ (2*R*,3*S*,4*R*,5*R*,8*R*,10*R*,11*R*,12*S*,13*S*,14*R*)-2-ethyl-3,4,10-trihydroxy-3,5,6,8,10,12,14-heptamethyl-15-oxo-11-{[3,4,6-trideoxy-3-(dimethylamino)- β -D-xylo-hexopyranosyl]oxy}-1-oxa-6-azacyclo pentadec-13-yl-2,6-dideoxy-3-*C*-methyl-3-*O*-methyl- α -L-*ribo*-hexopyranoside) is an azalide, a subclass of macrolide antibiotic. Aztreonam 2-({[(1*Z*)-1-(2-amino-1,3-thiazole-4-yl)-2-{{[(2*s*,3*s*)-2-methyl-4-oxo-1-sulfoazetid-3-yl]-2-oxoethylidamino}-2-oxy-2-methyl propanoic acid) is effective against a wide range of bacteria including *Citrobacter*, *Enterobacter*, *E. coli*, *Haemophilus*, *Klebsiella*, *Proteus* and *Serratia* species. Gemifloxacin^{5,6} (7-[(4*Z*)-3-(aminomethyl)-4-methoxyimino-pyrrolidin-1-yl]-1-

cyclopropyl-6-fluoro-4-oxo-1,8-naphthyridine-3-carboxylic acid) is an oral broad spectrum quinolone antibacterial agent. Kanamycin^{7,8} 6-*O*-(3-amino-3-deoxy- α -D-glucopyranosyl)-4-*O*-(6-amino-6-deoxy- α -D-glucopyranosyl)-2-deoxy-steptomine sulphate is an aminoglycoside bactericidal antibiotic and used to treat a wide variety of infections. And Clindamycin^{9–11} (methyl 7-chloro-6,7,8-trideoxy-6-{{[(4*R*)-1-methyl-4-propyl-L-prolyl]amino}-1-thio-L-threo- α -D-galactooctopyranoside). Most of the methods used for the determination of antibiotic drugs are instrumental and involve complicated techniques. In the present paper a new titrimetric method has been described for the determination of antibiotics under reference.

Results and discussion

The reaction conditions were established after studying effect of variables such as reaction time, concentration of the reagent, amount of reagent, sulphuric acid and reaction temperature. In the determination of Azithromycin,

Gemifloxacin, Aztreonam, Kanamycin in pure form and in their pharmaceutical preparation constant results were obtained at 10, 5, 10, 15 and 10 min respectively. A much more reaction time than the prescribed one does not improve results. The percentage recovery of sample was fairly low at a lesser reaction time due to incomplete reaction. It was also established that the prescribed concentration of the reagent (0.035 *N*) was suitable for accurate results. The effect of concentration of Cu^{III} reagent and sulphuric acid was studied and it was found that the recommended concentration of both reagents were suitable for the completion of reaction. While studying the effect of temperature it was observed that the reaction was completed at room temperature (25–30 °C). On heating the reaction mixture directly on flame or on boiling water bath inaccurate results were obtained. It may be due to decomposition of the reagent. Results given in Table 1 show % error, standard deviation (SD), and coefficient of variation (CV). This indicates that the suggested method is reproducible and precise. It can easily be adopted in any pharmaceutical laboratory.

Experimental

Reagents and solutions :

Potassiumdipertelluratocuprate(III) reagent^{13–15} $\text{K}_5\text{H}_4[\text{Cu}(\text{TeO}_6)_2] \cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.035 *M*) was prepared by adding copper sulphate (Merck) (7.0805 g), potassium tellurite (CDH) (15.8630 g), potassium persulphate (Loba-Chemie) (21.1010 g), potassium hydroxide (Merck) (40 g), to 400 mL of distilled water. The mixture was shaken thoroughly and boiled on hot plate for about 20 min. When the boiled mixture turned intensely red, the boiling was continued for another 20 min. The mixture was then cooled at room temperature, filtered through cindered glass crucible (G-4) and diluted to 500 mL with distilled water. If an excess of persulphate was present boiling for longer time is required for its complete decomposition (Test for presence of persulphate in prepared solution : Acidify 1 mL solution with dilute H_2SO_4 till no red colour appeared thus Cu^{III} converted to Cu^{II} . Add 5 mL of 0.5 *M* NaHCO_3 and 2 mL of 5% potassium iodide solution. Allowed it to stand for 2 min and then added two drops of starch solution. A blue color indicates the presence of persulphate). The alkaline solution of Cu^{III} prepared in

this way was fairly stable and the concentration remains practically unaltered for several months.

Standardization of Cu^{III} reagent :

Aliquots (5 mL) of the solution were treated with 5 mL of 0.02 *M* standardized arsenite solution. The mixture was allowed to stand for 3–4 min then acidified with 0.5 *M* H_2SO_4 till a green suspension disappeared and a clear solution was obtained. This solution was treated with 5 mL of 0.5 *M* NaCO_3 and back titrated the unconsumed arsenite with standard iodine solution (0.01 *N*) using starch as an indicator. A blank was also run.

Stock solution (Aqueous) of sodiumthiosulphate (0.01 *N*) (Merck) was prepared and standardized by (Merck) 0.01 *N* potassium dichromate solution iodometrically. Aqueous solution of potassium iodide (Baker analyzed reagent) and (10% w/v) starch were also prepared.

Sample solution :

Accurately weighed (100 mg) pure sample of Azithromycin, Azenam, Kenamycin, Gemifloxacin and Clindamycin were dissolved in distilled water in a 100 mL volumetric flask and solution made up to the mark to give a concentration of 1 mg/mL.

Tablets solution :

Twenty tablets of pharmaceutical products were crushed to a fine powder and powder equivalent to 100 mg of sample was taken in 100 mL calibrated volumetric flask and dissolved in minimum amount of distilled water. After getting a clear solution the flask was made upto the mark with distilled water.

Injections solution :

Solution of injection of the above compounds having an amount equivalent to 50 mg of pure sample were taken and dissolved in distilled water in 50 mL measuring flask to get a concentration of 1 mg/mL.

General procedure :

Aliquots containing 1–5 mg of the sample were taken in 100 mL stoppered conical flask and 5 mL of 0.035 *M* Cu^{III} reagent and 10 mL of 5 *N* H_2SO_4 was added to it. The reaction mixture was shaken thoroughly and allowed to react for required reaction time (5–15 min) at room temperature (25–30 °C). After the reaction was over, 5 mL of 10% potassium iodide was added to it and titrated

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against standardized sodium thiosulphate solution (0.01 *N*) using starch indicator. A blank experiment was also performed under identical conditions using all the reagents except the sample. The amount of the sample was calculated by the following expression.

Calculation :

For each experiment, the amount of compound was calculated by following expression :

$$\text{Weight of sample (mg)} = \frac{M \times N(B - S)}{n}$$

where, *M* = molecular weight of the sample, *N* = normality of sodium thiosulphate solution, *B* = volume of sodium thiosulphate solution for blank, *S* = volume of sodium thiosulphate solution for sample, *n* = stoichiometry of the reaction.

Table 1. Milligram determination of some antibiotic drugs in pure form and in their pharmaceutical preparations with potassiumdipertelluratocuprate(III) reagent

Sl. no.	Sample	Aliquots taken (mL)	Amount present ^a (mg)	Reaction time (min)	Molecularity (n)	Amount obtained by calculation ^b	Error (%)	SD	CV
1.	Azithromycin (Pure)	1	0.980	10	4	0.974	-0.60	0.0064	0.6571
		3	2.940	10	4	2.930	-0.50	0.0063	0.2150
		5	4.900	10	4	4.887	-0.02	0.0051	0.1044
A	AZEE 250 (Tab.)	1	0.968	10	4	0.955	-1.30	0.0083	0.8651
		3	2.904	10	4	2.902	-0.10	0.0076	0.2619
		5	4.840	10	4	4.830	-0.20	0.0067	0.1387
B	Azibest (Tab.)	1	9.917	10	4	0.907	-1.09	0.0031	0.3418
		3	2.751	10	4	2.733	-0.65	0.0029	0.1061
		5	4.585	10	4	4.564	-0.46	0.0031	0.0679
2.	Gemifloxacin (Pure)	1	0.984	5	2	0.973	-1.10	0.0062	0.6372
		2	2.952	5	2	2.933	-0.63	0.0052	0.1773
		3	4.920	5	2	4.906	-0.28	0.0051	0.1039
A	Gem One (Inj.)	1	0.946	5	2	0.934	-1.20	0.0071	0.7577
		3	2.838	5	2	2.816	-0.73	0.0051	0.1811
		5	4.730	5	2	4.720	-0.10	0.0048	0.1015
B	Gemez (Tab.)	1	0.932	5	2	0.922	-0.07	0.0021	0.2278
		3	2.796	5	2	2.778	-0.64	0.0022	0.0792
		5	4.660	5	2	4.642	-0.39	0.0033	0.0711
3.	Aztreonam (Pure)	1	0.990	10	3	0.986	-0.40	0.0078	0.7911
		3	2.970	10	3	2.960	-0.33	0.0061	0.2061
		5	4.950	10	3	4.935	-0.30	0.0064	0.1297
A	Azenam (Inj.)	1	0.972	10	3	0.958	-1.40	0.0076	0.7932
		3	2.916	10	3	2.903	-0.43	0.0058	0.1978
		5	4.860	10	3	4.847	-0.26	0.0062	0.1279
B	Treem (Inj.)	1	0.941	10	3	0.931	-1.06	0.0015	0.1611
		3	2.823	10	3	2.805	-0.64	0.0014	0.0499
		5	4.705	10	3	4.686	-0.40	0.0025	0.0534
4.	Kanamycin sulphate (Pure)	1	0.992	15	7	0.983	-0.90	0.0040	0.4069
		3	2.976	15	7	2.948	-0.80	0.0053	0.1798
		5	4.960	15	7	4.935	-0.05	0.0044	0.0892
A	Kanamac (Inj.)	1	0.982	15	7	0.976	-0.60	0.0033	0.3381
		3	2.946	15	7	2.942	-0.13	0.0078	0.2651
		5	4.910	15	7	4.907	-0.06	0.0044	0.0897

Table-1 (contd.)

B	Kencin (Inj.)	1	0.936	15	7	0.926	-1.01	0.0042	0.0710
		3	2.808	15	7	2.784	-0.86	0.0038	0.4536
		5	4.680	15	7	4.651	-0.62	0.0026	0.1365
5.	Clindamycin (Pure)	1	0.988	10	4	0.977	-1.10	0.0049	0.5015
		3	2.964	10	4	2.943	-0.70	0.0040	0.1359
		5	4.940	10	4	4.929	-0.22	0.0089	0.1806
A	Delacine (Inj.)	1	0.952	10	4	0.945	-0.70	0.0056	0.5926
		3	2.856	10	4	2.847	-0.30	0.0033	0.1159
		5	4.760	10	4	4.750	-0.20	0.0077	0.1621
B	Delcinex (Inj.)	1	0.918	10	4	0.908	-1.09	0.0034	0.3444
		3	2.754	10	4	2.737	-0.62	0.0032	0.1169
		5	4.590	10	4	4.573	-0.34	0.0025	0.0547

Where, Tab. = Tablet, Inj. = Injection. ^aIn each sample nine determinations were done. ^bAverage of nine determinations.

For testing authenticity of the recommended procedure standard deviation (SD) and coefficient of variation (CV) were also calculated. At least nine determinations were carried out and the results noted. The proposed method was further justified by recovery experiments through standard drug addition method. A known amount of the pure compound was taken and to this, varying amounts of pharmaceutical product of the same compounds

were added. The total amount of the sample was found by the usual method.

$$\% \text{ Recovery} = \frac{N(\sum XY) - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{N(\sum X^2) - (\sum X)^2} \times 100$$

where, N = total no. of observations, X = amount of drug added, Y = amount of drug obtain by calculation.

Table 2. Recovery experiments of antibiotic drugs by standard drug addition method

Name of the drugs	Sl. no.	Number of observation (N)	Amount present (Pure) (mg) (X)	Amount of drug added (mg) (X)	Total amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg) (Y)	Amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg) (Y)	XY	X^2	Recovery (%)
Azithromycin	1.	3	0.980	0.968	1.923	0.955	0.924	0.937	98.65
	2.	3	0.980	1.936	2.878	1.910	3.698	3.748	
	3.	3	0.980	2.904	3.833	2.865	8.319	8.433	
	4.	3	0.980	3.872	4.808	3.820	14.791	14.992	
			$\sum N = 12$		$\sum X = 9.680$		$\sum Y = 9.350$	$\sum XY = 27.732$	
Gemifloxacin	1.	3	0.984	0.946	1.870	0.934	0.883	0.895	93.93
	2.	3	0.984	1.892	2.714	1.868	3.534	3.579	
	3.	3	0.984	2.838	3.648	2.802	7.952	8.054	
	4.	3	0.984	3.784	4.612	3.736	14.137	14.319	
			$\sum N = 12$		$\sum X = 9.460$		$\sum Y = 9.340$	$\sum XY = 26.506$	
Aztreonam	1.	3	0.990	0.972	1.830	0.958	0.931	0.945	98.17
	2.	3	0.990	1.944	2.748	1.916	3.725	3.779	
	3.	3	0.990	2.916	3.604	2.874	8.381	8.503	
	4.	3	0.990	3.888	4.804	3.832	14.899	15.116	
			$\sum N = 12$		$X = 9.720$		$\sum Y = 9.680$	$\sum XY = 27.936$	

Table-2 (contd.)

Kanamycin sulphate	1.	3	0.992	0.982	1.958	0.976	0.958	0.964	98.58
	2.	3	0.992	1.964	2.934	1.952	3.834	3.857	
	3.	3	0.992	2.946	3.910	2.928	8.626	8.679	
	4.	3	0.992	3.928	4.886	3.904	15.335	15.429	
	$\Sigma N = 12$		$\Sigma X = 9.820$			$\Sigma Y = 9.760$	$\Sigma XY = 28.753$	$\Sigma X^2 = 28.929$	
Clindamycin	1.	3	0.988	0.952	1.897	0.945	0.899	0.906	99.29
	2.	3	0.988	1.904	2.842	1.890	3.598	3.625	
	3.	3	0.988	2.856	3.787	2.835	8.097	8.157	
	4.	3	0.988	3.808	4.732	3.780	14.394	14.501	
	$\Sigma N = 12$		$\Sigma X = 9.520$			$\Sigma Y = 9.440$	$\Sigma XY = 26.988$	$\Sigma X^2 = 27.189$	

Conclusion

Survey of literature shows that Cu^{III} has widely been used for the analysis of several groups of compound but there is no reference regarding estimation of the compounds referred in the papers. Our experiments show that the estimation of antibiotics by this reagent is quite satisfactory and accurate. For every compound reaction condition were developed. Reaction time variations, concentration of reagent, reaction temperature were studied and standard method was developed. Stoichiometry of reaction was also established for every compound. To prove the authenticity of the method, % recovery and recovery experiments were done. For each sample size at least nine determinations were done and result calculated.

Interferences :

Excipients like starch, calcium carbonate, sodium carbonate, cellulose, magnesium trisilicate, tricalcium phosphate and gum acacia if present in the pharmaceutical preparations do not interfere in the estimation.

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